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Impact of Social Media on Students' Academic Performance

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Abstract

Social Media, the driver of every minute information has established a tremendous pace among the youths. Social media has become a daily necessity in this area. No doubt it has given a great platform for any individual to exchange ideas and grab information from worldwide. Smart phones and internet connection are all requirements and everything is just on a click of button. It has been observed that younger generation is very much prone to social media. So, this paper is an attempt to study the impact of social media on the university students.

The result shows that there is significant relationship between time spent on social media sites and academic works. It also revealed that the nature of social media activities which the student engages in does not have any significant impact on the student academic performance. A sample of 50 students is taken into consideration. Google forms are used in collecting data. All the respondents in the study have their own smart Phone with internet facilities. It is also found that with the use of social media the academic life of the students affected positively as well as negatively too.

Keywords: Internet, Social media, Academic work, Academic performance.

1. Introduction

Social media is an internet-based form of communication. Social media platforms allow users

to have conversations, share information and create web content. There are many forms of social media, including blogs, social networking sites, photo-sharing sites, instant messaging, video-sharing sites, podcasts, widgets, virtual worlds, and more. The internet has created a platform for millions of computers at numerous sites in various countries, belonging to thousands of businesses, governments, research institution, educational institutions and other organizations to link up with one another.

It provides a very rich medium for information dissemination, exchange and collaborative interaction among individuals and computers without regards for geographical limitation of space. Social networking has become a common international trend which has spread across almost every corner of the world. The Use of Social media sites have exploded and evolved into an online platform where people create content, share it, bookmark it and network at a prodigious rate. Because of its ease of use, speed and reach, social media is fast changing the public discourse in society and setting trends and agenda in topics that range from the environment and politics to technology and the entertainment industry.

In the last ten years, the online world has changed dramatically, thanks to the invention of social media, young men and women now exchange ideas, feelings, personal information, pictures and videos at a truly astonishing rate. The increased use of Social Networking Websites has become a social norm and way of life for people from all over the world. Teenagers and young adults have especially embraced these sites as a way to connect with their peers around the globe, share information, reinvent their personalities, and showcase their social lives. With these developments in technology social networking sites have become more and more popular among students and a major concern have arose over how the use of social media sites among undergraduate students affects their academic performances.

2. Methodology

Data was collected using primary data set through the distribution of Questionnaire through Google Forms is used and convenient sample is being used. In this study, Students from Kolhapur colleges were being selected. The reason for choosing the sample is that as the topic is related with social media and academic performance, so the students are taken as they mostly use phones and laptops. 12 questionnaires are distributed to 60 students but only 50 responses could be received.

Designation of the Respondent:

Diploma	Bachelors	Masters	Total
2	45	3	50

Out of 50 respondents, it is seen that many of the respondents i.e. 45 belongs to Bachelor's course from Computer departments of the Colleges, whereas only 2 responses are from Diploma Course and 3 from Master Course.

Table 1: Demographic Distribution of respondents

Students Demographic Details(n=50)		
Gender	Male	48%
	Female	52%
Age	16-19	31.7%
	20-23	68.3%
Academic Degree	Diploma	3%
	Bachelor's	91.8%
	Master	5.2%

There was a total of 50 responses received. The demographics were 52% females and 48% males. The majority of the respondents were between 20-23 years old and they made up 68.3% of the respondents. The rest of the 31.7% were 16-19 years old. Most of the response from Bachelors.

3. Data Analysis

The purpose of this study is to investigate the impact of social media on students in the Colleges. A descriptive approach for data analysis was considered. Response questions are coded, and categorized within each question to determine similar answer. Repetitive content of responses was identified. Finally, frequency counts of frequently occurring responses were tabulated and converted to percentages for reporting purposes. The section below describes the detailed findings of the survey.

4. Result

The survey was done to get an understanding of the experience and perception of students about the Social Media. The survey Results are described below.

Figure. 1. Percentage of students who have Social Media sites.

Each and every respondent i.e. 50 students have their own accounts in various social networking sites.

Table 2: Survey Question to Student's about Social Media

Survey Questions	Options	Response (%)
Do you Use Phone or Laptop?	Yes No	98% 2%
Do You have Social Media Accounts?	Yes No	98% 2%
Most Popular Social Media Platform?	WhatsApp Instagram	51% 49%
Do you think use of social medial has affected your study timing?	Yes No	40.8% 59.2%
Purpose of Using Social Media Platforms	Academic Purpose For Chatting For Fun Internet Shopping	55.1% 6.1%? 30.6% 8.2%
Do you feel more attracted towards social media compared to study	Yes No	51% 49%
Do you consider yourself addicted to social media	Yes No	24.5% 75.5%
Social media use had affected their relationships with their family members and friends.	Yes No	26.5% 73.5%
Time spent on social media at night.	1-2Hrs 2-3Hrs -3Hrs+	75.5% 18.4% 6.1%
The time spent by students on social media.	Any spare moment Meal Time During Social Occasions	63.3% 24.5% 12.2%
When Dose College Starts	7AM 8AM 11AM	6.2% 57.1% 36.7%

The study is about determining the impact of most popular factor of modern age social Media usage on the academic performances of the students. What activates performed by student on

these Medias and how much time they spent on these sites in their routine life?

Social networking site use is prevalent among university students because of the availability of smartphones and easy access to such sites through home computers. It is found that each and every Student have their own phones. Social media use reduces the amount of time that students spend on academic activities. Only 44.1% of the students used social media for academic purposes, and a majority of them (45-50%) used social media for non-academic purposes to chat with others (i.e., WhatsApp, Facebook, Instagram, Snapchat) and browsed social networking sites to pass time. At present, social media platforms can be used to retrieve necessary information that serves educational purposes. However, social media use negatively affected the academic progress. Most participants used social media platforms to chat rather than for academic purposes.

Students who spend more time on social media sites are likely to demonstrate poor academic performance. This is because they spend time chatting online and making friends on social media sites instead of reading books. This has a negative effect on their academic performance. Therefore, it is important to determine the duration of time that they spend on social media sites and the proportion of time that is spent on social media sites for academic purposes. 76% of the students reported that they were addicted to social media, and has significantly affected there learning activities and 52% of them are more attracted towards social media than studies. University students, especially those who feel addicted to social networking sites, access these platforms through their smartphones not only at home but also on campus. Social media plays an important role in education. However, because several social networking sites exist, students spend more time chatting, watching movies, shopping, and playing games rather than on educational activities.

Because they felt drawn toward new social media platforms, they felt compelled to quickly complete their academic assignments and spend their remaining time playing games or chatting with others through social media platforms. Social media use has both positive and negative effects.

However, the negative effects are more pronounced because students tend to use such platforms to have fun and pass time rather than for academic purposes. This may distract them from learning and academic activities. This study determined the percentage of students who felt more drawn toward social media than toward academic activities and prioritizing of using social media for fun than academic purposes. The findings underscore the importance of creating awareness about the negative effects of such habits on academic performance among students. In the present study 18-75% of the students spend one to four hours on social media during day and night, thus majority of the students spent a total of eight hours on social media every day. Although spending a lot of time on one's mobile phone is not considered to be an abnormal behavior pattern.

However, prolonged social media use has mental health effects and young adults are the most vulnerable one. Studies have shown that social media use is associated with mental disorders, including depression and anxiety. Although, Social media helps individuals connect with others and develop new relationships. However, such relationships tend to be more formal and transient. Social media users tend to not share close and trusting relationships with their online friends. Moreover, these relationships cannot be compared to the relationships that are developed with friends and family members through face-to-face interactions.

26.5% of the students reported that excessive time spending on social media has negative impact on their relationship with family and friends. Relying solely on social media to build and maintain relationships can lead to loneliness, alienation, and depression. Smartphones create a psychological distance between individuals by decreasing face-to-face interactions between family members and friends; and this can negatively affect the quality of time spent on these relationships.

Face-to-face interpersonal communication is an important determinant of well-being. Therefore, individuals should spend their free time with their friends and families in person rather than through social media. This may have a more positive impact on mood, enhance psychological satisfaction, and prevent loneliness and depression. 63.3% of them reported that they spent their free time on social media. In this study, the most widely used application was Instagram (49%) and WhatsApp (51%). Further, extensive smartphone use can cause addiction and hamper one's ability to enjoy his or her free time with family members and friends. Among adults, social media use leads to reduced physical activity and increased sitting durations. As a result, sedentary behaviors are commonly observed. Sleeping for fewer hours than the recommended duration on a regular basis is associated with attention, behavior, and learning problems. Late-night social media use is prevalent among adults.

As a result, they do not get adequate sleep. Sleep disturbances caused by excessive social media use at night adversely affect daytime learning on campus and lead to poor concentration during lectures. Because many students are addicted to social media and use such platforms for nonacademic purposes, it is important to determine the negative effects of social media use. In the present study it was observed that student go to late night sleep, they are deprived of good sleep duration as the college starts at 8 for about 57% of the students, and the students has

reason social media for late night sleep. Sleep deprivation is rapidly becoming prevalent, and it has frequently been linked to late-night use of social networking sites, television viewing, and gaming. Mobile phone use before bedtime is a common habit among many young adults. In this study, the students slept for fewer hours than the recommended sleep duration because of late-night social media site use. This can lead to a delayed bedtime, sleep loss, and irregular sleep-wake patterns. Poor sleep quality results in increased tiredness during the day.

5. Conclusion

Social media has numerous boons to a student's life that has helped them to develop and groom them with the era of science and continue their study even sitting at home. Social media networking sites like Facebook, YouTube are very much involved in study activities. Students too are very much active on these sites, using both for entertainment and study purpose. The mass from every corner to exchange ones ideas and thoughts and students, research scholars are greatly benefitted from it to access and furnish their work precisely. The students are able to clear their doubts regarding any minute topic and can get help from the top educators which has brought a positive attitude towards study through social media networking sites but most of the students use these sites usually for entertainment purpose which has engaged them more with the smart gadgets which is a negative sign. So it proves to be both positive and negative aspects. Where on the one side students are facilitated with their education to be better and are benefitted and growing with better influential results but on the other side it has also reaped students from the real world and has engaged them with the virtual things. So proper use of social media networking sites is to be maintained and should be utilized to its optimum for future betterment. Therefore it is our suggestion that for students to be more productive, the need to minimize the time they spend engaging on social media activities.

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